

NYM0921	2 (D)	Assessment of NBS benefits	X	X	X	X		X	X	X	X	X	X
NYM1121	2 (C)	Tools to engage citizens		X	X	X			X		X		
NYM1221	2 (A)	Use grazing management and animal impact as farm and ecosystem development tools				X							X
NYM1421	2 (A)	Agroforestry	X										X
	3 (A)	Hedge and planted fence											
	3 (D)	Use of pre-existing vegetation	X		X	X	X	X		X		X	
NYM1321	1 (A)	Limit or prevent specific uses and practices				X						X	
		Planning tools for biodiversity, green infrastructure, and ecosystem services	X	X	X	X				X			X
	2 (C)	Heritage Park		X		X							X
NYM1821	1 (A)	Limit or prevent specific uses and practices				X						X	
		Planning tools for biodiversity, green infrastructure, and ecosystem services	X	X	X	X				X			X
	2 (C)	Heritage Park		X		X							X
NYM1921	1 (A)	Limit or prevent specific uses and practices				X						X	
	2 (C)	Planning tools for biodiversity, green infrastructure, and ecosystem services	X	X	X	X				X			X
NYM2321	1 (A)	Limit or prevent specific uses and practices				X						X	
	2 (A)	Incorporating manure, compost, biosolids, or incorporating crop residues to enhance carbon storage				X						X	
	3 (E)	Target ponds/wetland creation to trap sediment/pollution runoff in farmed landscape	X									X	
NYM2521	2 (A)	Enrichment planting in degraded and regenerating forests	X			X							X
	3 (A)	Create and preserve habitats and shelters for biodiversity		X						X			X
NYM2621		Agroforestry	X										X
	2 (A)	Enrichment planting in degraded and regenerating forests	X			X							X
		Planning tools for biodiversity, green infrastructure, and ecosystem services	X	X	X	X				X			X
	2 (C)	Heritage Park		X		X							X

	3 (A)	Create and preserve habitats and shelters for biodiversity		X						X			X
	3 (D)	Use of pre-existing vegetation	X		X	X	X	X		X		X	
NYM2721	2 (C)	Heritage Park		X		X							X
	3 (D)	Systems for erosion control				X		X		X		X	
	3 (E)	Rivers or streams, including remeandering, re-opening Blue corridors				X		X	X	X	X	X	X
NYM2821	1 (A)	Limit or prevent specific uses and practices				X						X	
	2 (A)	Soil improvement and conservation measures				X							X
		Incorporating manure, compost, biosolids, or incorporating crop residues to enhance carbon storage				X						X	
	2 (C)	Planning tools for biodiversity, green infrastructure, and ecosystem services	X	X	X	X				X			X
		Tools to engage citizens		X	X	X			X		X		
3 (E)	Rivers or streams, including remeandering, re-opening Blue corridors				X		X	X	X	X	X	X	
NYM2121	2 (C)	Heritage Park		X		X							X
	3 (D)	Use of pre-existing vegetation	X		X	X	X	X		X		X	
NYM1122	2 (A)	Agroforestry	X										X
		Enrichment planting in degraded and regenerating forests	X			X							X
	2 (C)	Planning tools for biodiversity, green infrastructure, and ecosystem services	X	X	X	X				X			X
		Tools to engage citizens		X	X	X			X		X		
		Green belts	X		X		X	X					
	3 (A)	Create and preserve habitats and shelters for biodiversity		X						X			X
3 (D)	Systems for erosion control				X		X		X		X		
NYM0522	1 (A)	Limit or prevent specific uses and practices				X						X	

		Soil improvement and conservation measures				X							X
	2 (A)	Incorporating manure, compost, biosolids, or incorporating crop residues to enhance carbon storage				X						X	
		Limit or prevent specific uses and practices				X						X	
	1 (A)	Protect forests from clearing and degradation from logging, fire, and unsustainable levels of non-timber resource extraction	X	X		X	X	X		X	X	X	X
NYM4121	3 (A)	Integrated weed management											
	2 (A)	Hedge and planted fence											
		Planning tools for biodiversity, green infrastructure, and ecosystem services	X	X	X	X				X			X
	2 (C)	Green belts	X		X		X	X					
	3 (A)	Create and preserve habitats and shelters for biodiversity		X						X			X
	3 (D)	Use of pre-existing vegetation	X		X	X	X	X		X		X	
NYM3721		Plant trees/ hedges/perennial grass strips to intercept surface run-off											
	1 (A)	Limit or prevent specific uses and practices				X						X	
NYM3421	3 (D)	Use of pre-existing vegetation	X		X	X	X	X		X		X	
	2 (A)	Agroforestry	X										X
		Planning tools for biodiversity, green infrastructure, and ecosystem services	X	X	X	X				X			X
	2 (C)	Green belts	X		X		X	X					
NYM1922	3 (D)	Use of pre-existing vegetation	X		X	X	X	X		X		X	
	1 (A)	Limit or prevent specific uses and practices				X						X	
	2 (C)	Planning tools for biodiversity, green infrastructure, and ecosystem services	X	X	X	X				X			X
NYM2622	3 (D)	Use of pre-existing vegetation	X		X	X	X	X		X		X	
NYM2722	2 (C)	Heritage Park		X		X							X
		Hedge and planted fence											
NYM2921	2 (A)	Soil improvement and conservation measures				X							X

	2 (C)	Heritage Park		X		X							X	
		Tools to engage citizens		X	X	X			X		X			
		Green belts	X		X		X	X						
	3 (A)	Create and preserve habitats and shelters for biodiversity		X						X			X	
	3 (D)	Use of pre-existing vegetation	X		X	X	X	X		X		X		
NYM0422		Tools to engage citizens		X	X	X			X		X			
	3 (D)	Use of pre-existing vegetation	X		X	X	X	X		X		X		
NYM2222	1 (A)	Limit or prevent specific uses and practices				X							X	
	2 (C)	Planning tools for biodiversity, green infrastructure, and ecosystem services	X	X	X	X				X			X	
	3 (E)	Rivers or streams, including remeandering, re-opening Blue corridors				X			X	X	X	X	X	
NYM2422	2 (A)	Soil improvement and conservation measures				X							X	
	2 (C)	Planning tools for biodiversity, green infrastructure, and ecosystem services	X	X	X	X				X			X	
	3 (A)	Create and preserve habitats and shelters for biodiversity		X						X			X	
	3 (D)	Use of pre-existing vegetation	X		X	X	X	X		X		X		
NYM4222		Agroforestry	X										X	
		Soil improvement and conservation measures				X							X	
	2 (A)	Enrichment planting in degraded and regenerating forests	X			X							X	
	2 (B)	Integrated coastal zone management	X			X		X		X			X	
		Heritage Park		X		X							X	
		Planning tools for biodiversity, green infrastructure, and ecosystem services	X	X	X	X				X			X	
		Tools to engage citizens		X	X	X			X		X			
	2 (C)	Green belts	X		X		X	X						
	3 (A)	Create and preserve habitats and shelters for biodiversity		X						X			X	
3 (D)	Use of pre-existing vegetation	X		X	X	X	X		X		X			

	3 (E)	Rivers or streams, including remeandering, re-opening Blue corridors						X				X	X	X	X	X
	3 (F)	Re-establish and restore previous intertidal habitat by de-poldering or coastal realignment	X					X	X			X	X	X		X

PROJECT	TYPE	NBS	Challenges										Ecosystem Services				
			Climate mitigation and adaptation	Water management	Coastal resilience	Green space management	Air quality	Urban regeneration	Participatory planning and governance	Social justice and social cohesion	Public health and wellbeing	Potential of economic opportunities and green jobs	Provisioning services: (F), (W), (P), (E) *	Regulation and maintenance: (CS&R), (WP), (AQ), (EP), (FP), (MP&H), (P&DC), (CP)*	Cultural: (R), (I), (S) *		
NYM0221	2 (A)	Use grazing management and animal impact as farm and ecosystem development tools									X	X		X		(MP & H)	(I)
	3 (D)	Use of pre-existing vegetation		X		X	X	X				X	X		(W)	(WP), (AQ), (EP), (FP), (CS&R)	(R), (I)
NYM0321	2 (D)	Assessment of NBS benefits	X	X	X	X					X		X		(W)	(FP), (MP&H), (EP)	(I)
NYM0121	2 (A)	Agro-ecological practices	X	X							X	X		X	(W), (F)	(AQ), (CS&R), (WP), (FP)	(R), (I)
		Deep-rooted plants and minimum or conservation tillage										X		X		(MP&H)	(R), (I)
		Soil improvement and conservation measures		X							X	X	X	X		(WP), (EP), (CS&R)	(R), (I)
		Incorporating manure, compost, biosolids, or incorporating crop residues to enhance carbon storage		X												(W)	(MP&H)

		Increase soil water holding capacity and infiltration rates		X					X	X	X	X	(W)	(FP)	
	3 (D)	Systems for erosion control	X	X		X							(W)	(CS&R), (WP), (EP), (AQ), (FP), (MP&H)	(R), (I)
NYM0421	1 (A)	Limit or prevent specific uses and practices	X	X		X	X	X		X	X		(W)	(AQ), (EP), (FP), (CS&R)	(R), (I)
	3 (C)	Urban water management		X		X	X	X		X		X	(W)	(CS&R), (WP), (FP)	(R)
NYM0521	1 (A)	Limit or prevent specific uses and practices	X	X		X	X	X		X	X		(W)	(AQ), (EP), (FP), (CS&R)	(R), (I)
		Planning tools for biodiversity, green infrastructure, and ecosystem services	X		X				X	X		X		(FP), (MP&H)	(I)
	2 (C)	Heritage Park	X	X		X	X	X		X	X			(MP&H)	(R), (S)
NYM0921	2 (D)	Assessment of NBS benefits	X	X	X	X			X		X		(W)	(FP), (MP&H), (EP)	(I)
NYM1121	2 (C)	Tools to engage citizens	X			X		X	X	X	X	X			(R), (I)
NYM1221	2 (A)	Use grazing management and animal impact as farm and ecosystem development tools							X	X		X		(MP & H)	(I)
NYM1421	2 (A)	Agroforestry	X											(MP & H), (CS&R)	(R), (I)
	3 (A)	Hedge and planted fence													
	3 (D)	Use of pre-existing vegetation		X		X	X	X		X	X		(W)	(WP), (AQ), (EP), (FP), (CS&R)	(R), (I)
NYM1321	1 (A)	Limit or prevent specific uses and practices	X	X		X	X	X		X	X		(W)	(AQ), (EP), (FP), (CS&R)	(R), (I)
		Planning tools for biodiversity, green infrastructure, and ecosystem services	X		X				X	X		X		(FP), (MP&H)	(I)
	2 (C)	Heritage Park	X	X		X	X	X		X	X			(MP&H)	(R), (S)
NYM1821	1 (A)	Limit or prevent specific uses and practices	X	X		X	X	X		X	X		(W)	(AQ), (EP), (FP), (CS&R)	(R), (I)
	2 (C)	Planning tools for biodiversity, green infrastructure, and ecosystem services	X		X				X	X		X		(FP), (MP&H)	(I)

		Heritage Park	X	X		X	X	X		X	X			(MP&H)	(R), (S)
NYM1921	1 (A)	Limit or prevent specific uses and practices	X	X		X	X	X		X	X		(W)	(AQ), (EP), (FP), (CS&R)	(R), (I)
	2 (C)	Planning tools for biodiversity, green infrastructure, and ecosystem services	X		X			X	X	X		X		(FP), (MP&H)	(I)
NYM2321	1 (A)	Limit or prevent specific uses and practices	X	X		X	X	X		X	X		(W)	(AQ), (EP), (FP), (CS&R)	(R), (I)
	2 (A)	Incorporating manure, compost, biosolids, or incorporating crop residues to enhance carbon storage		X									(W)	(MP&H)	(I), (S)
	3 (E)	Target ponds/wetland creation to trap sediment/pollution runoff in farmed landscape		X		X	X	X		X		X	(W)	(WP), (AQ), (EP), (FP),(CS&R)	(R), (I)
NYM2521	2 (A)	Enrichment planting in degraded and regenerating forests	X	X			X		X	X				(MP&H), (CS&R)	(R), (I)
	3 (A)	Create and preserve habitats and shelters for biodiversity		X		X	X				X		(E)	(AQ), (FP), (MP&H), (CS&R)	(R), (I), (S)
NYM2621	2 (A)	Agroforestry	X											(MP & H), (CS&R)	(R), (I)
		Enrichment planting in degraded and regenerating forests	X	X			X		X	X				(MP&H), (CS&R)	(R), (I)
	2 (C)	Planning tools for biodiversity, green infrastructure, and ecosystem services	X		X			X	X	X		X		(FP), (MP&H)	(I)
		Heritage Park	X	X		X	X	X		X	X			(MP&H)	(R), (S)
	3 (A)	Create and preserve habitats and shelters for biodiversity		X		X	X				X		(E)	(AQ), (FP), (MP&H), (CS&R)	(R), (I), (S)
	3 (D)	Use of pre-existing vegetation		X		X	X	X		X	X		(W)	(WP), (AQ), (EP), (FP),(CS&R)	(R),(I)
NYM2721	2 (C)	Heritage Park	X	X		X	X	X		X	X			(MP&H)	(R), (S)
	3 (D)	Systems for erosion control	X	X		X							(W)	(CS&R), (WP), (EP), (AQ), (FP), (MP&H)	(R), (I)

	3 (E)	Rivers or streams, including remeandering, re-opening Blue corridors		X		X	X			X	X		(F)	(WP), (FP), (MP&H), (CS&R), (EP)	(R), (I)	
NYM2821	1 (A)	Limit or prevent specific uses and practices	X	X		X	X	X		X	X		(W)	(AQ), (EP), (FP), (CS&R)	(R), (I)	
	2 (A)	Soil improvement and conservation measures		X					X	X	X	X		(WP), (EP), (CS&R)	(R), (I)	
		Incorporating manure, compost, biosolids, or incorporating crop residues to enhance carbon storage		X										(W)	(MP&H)	(I), (S)
	2 (C)	Planning tools for biodiversity, green infrastructure, and ecosystem services	X		X			X	X	X		X			(FP), (MP&H)	(I)
		Tools to engage citizens	X			X		X	X	X	X	X				(R), (I)
	3 (E)	Rivers or streams, including remeandering, re-opening Blue corridors		X		X	X			X	X			(F)	(WP), (FP), (MP&H), (CS&R), (EP)	(R), (I)
NYM2121	2 (C)	Heritage Park	X	X		X	X	X		X	X			(MP&H)	(R), (S)	
	3 (D)	Use of pre-existing vegetation		X		X	X	X		X	X		(W)	(WP), (AQ), (EP), (FP), (CS&R)	(R), (I)	
NYM1122	2 (A)	Agroforestry	X											(MP & H), (CS&R)	(R), (I)	
		Enrichment planting in degraded and regenerating forests	X	X			X		X	X					(MP&H), (CS&R)	(R), (I)
	2 (C)	Planning tools for biodiversity, green infrastructure, and ecosystem services	X		X			X	X	X		X			(FP), (MP&H)	(I)
		Tools to engage citizens	X			X		X	X	X	X	X				(R), (I)
		Green belts	X	X		X	X			X	X				(AQ), (FP), (CS&R)	(R)
	3 (A)	Create and preserve habitats and shelters for biodiversity		X		X	X				X			(E)	(AQ), (FP), (MP&H), (CS&R)	(R), (I), (S)
3 (D)	Systems for erosion control	X	X		X								(W)	(CS&R), (WP), (EP), (AQ), (FP), (MP&H)	(R), (I)	
NYM0522	1 (A)	Limit or prevent specific uses and practices	X	X		X	X	X		X	X		(W)	(AQ), (EP), (FP), (CS&R)	(R), (I)	

		Soil improvement and conservation measures		X					X	X	X	X		(WP), (EP), (CS&R)	(R), (I)
	2 (A)	Incorporating manure, compost, biosolids, or incorporating crop residues to enhance carbon storage		X									(W)	(MP&H)	(I), (S)
NYM4121		Limit or prevent specific uses and practices	X	X		X	X	X		X	X		(W)	(AQ), (EP), (FP), (CS&R)	(R), (I)
	1 (A)	Protect forests from clearing and degradation from logging, fire, and unsustainable levels of non-timber resource extraction	X						X	X		X		(EP), (FP), (MP&H), (CS&R)	
	3 (A)	Integrated weed management													
NYM3721	2 (A)	Hedge and planted fence													
		Planning tools for biodiversity, green infrastructure, and ecosystem services	X		X			X	X	X		X		(FP), (MP&H)	(I)
	2 (C)	Green belts	X	X		X	X			X	X			(AQ), (FP), (CS&R)	(R)
	3 (A)	Create and preserve habitats and shelters for biodiversity			X		X	X			X		(E)	(AQ), (FP), (MP&H), (CS&R)	(R), (I), (S)
	3 (D)	Use of pre-existing vegetation			X		X	X	X		X	X	(W)	(WP), (AQ), (EP), (FP), (CS&R)	(R), (I)
		Plant trees/ hedges/perennial grass strips to intercept surface run-off													
NYM3421	1 (A)	Limit or prevent specific uses and practices	X	X		X	X	X		X	X		(W)	(AQ), (EP), (FP), (CS&R)	(R), (I)
	3 (D)	Use of pre-existing vegetation			X		X	X	X		X	X	(W)	(WP), (AQ), (EP), (FP), (CS&R)	(R), (I)
NYM1922	2 (A)	Agroforestry	X											(MP & H), (CS&R)	(R), (I)
		Planning tools for biodiversity, green infrastructure, and ecosystem services	X		X			X	X	X		X		(FP), (MP&H)	(I)
	2 (C)	Green belts	X	X		X	X			X	X			(AQ), (FP), (CS&R)	(R)
	3 (D)	Use of pre-existing vegetation			X		X	X	X		X	X	(W)	(WP), (AQ), (EP), (FP), (CS&R)	(R), (I)

NYM2622	1 (A)	Limit or prevent specific uses and practices	X	X		X	X	X		X	X		(W)	(AQ), (EP), (FP), (CS&R)	(R), (I)	
	2 (C)	Planning tools for biodiversity, green infrastructure, and ecosystem services	X		X			X	X	X		X		(FP), (MP&H)	(I)	
	3 (D)	Use of pre-existing vegetation		X		X	X	X		X	X		(W)	(WP), (AQ), (EP), (FP),(CS&R)	(R),(I)	
NYM2722	2 (C)	Heritage Park	X	X		X	X	X		X	X			(MP&H)	(R), (S)	
NYM2921	2 (A)	Hedge and planted fence														
		Soil improvement and conservation measures		X					X	X	X	X		(WP), (EP), (CS&R)	(R), (I)	
	2 (C)	Heritage Park	X	X		X	X	X		X	X			(MP&H)	(R), (S)	
		Tools to engage citizens	X			X		X	X	X	X	X				(R), (I)
		Green belts	X	X		X	X			X	X			(AQ), (FP), (CS&R)	(R)	
	3 (A)	Create and preserve habitats and shelters for biodiversity		X		X	X				X		(E)	(AQ), (FP), (MP&H), (CS&R)	(R), (I), (S)	
3 (D)	Use of pre-existing vegetation		X		X	X	X		X	X		(W)	(WP), (AQ), (EP), (FP),(CS&R)	(R),(I)		
NYM0422		Tools to engage citizens	X			X		X	X	X	X				(R), (I)	
	3 (D)	Use of pre-existing vegetation		X		X	X	X		X	X		(W)	(WP), (AQ), (EP), (FP),(CS&R)	(R),(I)	
NYM2222	1 (A)	Limit or prevent specific uses and practices	X	X		X	X	X		X	X		(W)	(AQ), (EP), (FP), (CS&R)	(R), (I)	
	2 (C)	Planning tools for biodiversity, green infrastructure, and ecosystem services	X		X			X	X	X		X		(FP), (MP&H)	(I)	
	3 (E)	Rivers or streams, including remeandering, re-opening Blue corridors		X		X	X			X	X		(F)	(WP), (FP), (MP&H), (CS&R), (EP)	(R), (I)	
NYM2422	2 (A)	Soil improvement and conservation measures		X					X	X	X	X		(WP), (EP), (CS&R)	(R), (I)	
	2 (C)	Planning tools for biodiversity, green infrastructure, and ecosystem services	X		X			X	X	X		X		(FP), (MP&H)	(I)	

	3 (A)	Create and preserve habitats and shelters for biodiversity		X		X	X						(E)	(AQ), (FP), (MP&H), (CS&R)	(R), (I), (S)	
	3 (D)	Use of pre-existing vegetation		X		X	X	X		X	X		(W)	(WP), (AQ), (EP), (FP),(CS&R)	(R),(I)	
NYM4222	2 (A)	Agroforestry	X											(MP & H), (CS&R)	(R), (I)	
		Soil improvement and conservation measures		X					X	X	X	X		(WP), (EP), (CS&R)	(R), (I)	
	Enrichment planting in degraded and regenerating forests	X	X			X		X	X					(MP&H), (CS&R)	(R), (I)	
	2 (B)	Integrated coastal zone management	X	X					X	X		X	(W),(F)	(AQ), (CS&R), (WP), (FP)		
	2 (C)	Heritage Park	X	X		X	X	X		X	X				(MP&H)	(R), (S)
		Planning tools for biodiversity, green infrastructure, and ecosystem services	X		X			X	X	X	X	X			(FP), (MP&H)	(I)
		Tools to engage citizens	X			X		X	X	X	X	X				(R), (I)
	2 (C)	Green belts	X	X		X	X			X	X			(AQ), (FP), (CS&R)	(R)	
	3 (A)	Create and preserve habitats and shelters for biodiversity		X		X	X				X		(E)	(AQ), (FP), (MP&H), (CS&R)	(R), (I), (S)	
	3 (D)	Use of pre-existing vegetation		X		X	X	X		X	X		(W)	(WP), (AQ), (EP), (FP),(CS&R)	(R),(I)	
3 (E)	Rivers or streams, including remeandering, re-opening Blue corridors		X		X	X			X	X		(F)	(WP), (FP), (MP&H), (CS&R), (EP)	(R), (I)		
3 (F)	Re-establish and restore previous intertidal habitat by de-poldering or coastal realignment	X		X	X	X				X		(F), (W)	(EP), (FP), (CS&R), (MP&H)			

Type 1	Type 2	Type 3
Better use of protected/ natural ecosystems - No or minimal intervention in ecosystems, with the objectives of maintaining or improving the delivery of a range of ES both inside and outside of these preserved ecosystems	NBS for sustainability and multifunctionality of managed ecosystems - Definition and implementation of management approaches that develop sustainable and multifunctional ecosystems and landscapes (extensively or intensively managed), which improves the delivery of selected ES compared to what would be obtained with a more conventional intervention	Design and management of new ecosystems – Managing ecosystems in very intrusive ways or even creating new ecosystems (e.g., artificial ecosystems with new assemblages of organisms for green roofs and walls to mitigate city warming and clean polluted air).

NbS typology/classification (A1) according to Eggermont et al. (2015)

Ecosystem Services			
(F)	Food, crops, wild foods, and spices	(P&DC)	Pest and disease control
(w)	Water	(CP)	Crop pollination
(P)	Pharmaceuticals, biochemicals, and industry. Products	(N)	Nutrient dispersal & and cycling
(E)	Energy	(SD)	Seed dispersal
(CS&R)	Carbon sequestration and climate regulation	(SFC)	Soil formation and composting
(WP)	Water purification	(P)	Primary production
(AQ)	Air quality regulation	(R)	Recreation
(EP)	Erosion prevention	(I)	Intellectual and aesthetic appreciation
(FP)	Flood protection	(S)	Spiritual and symbolic appreciation
(MP&H)	Maintaining populations and habitats		

(Think Nature, 2019, p. 193, Annex 2)